

Note: This is a pre-final version. The final version of this article will appear in *Proceedings of the 6th Congress of Turcology "Studies on the Turkic World – Multidisciplinary Perspectives" September 19-21 2022, University of Warsaw, Warsaw, Poland.*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10494487>

ON MONGOLIC BACK BORROWINGS IN KYRGYZ

Rysbek Alimov¹

Abstract

As a rule, back borrowings emerge when two languages co-exist and have centuries-old and in-depth contact with each other. The study of this phenomenon allows us to trace many features of mutual influences of contact languages, including the time of copying, certain phonetic shapes, or semantic features that the copied words possessed or obtained during the process of copying, as well as reveal the phenomenon of borrowing in all its diversity.

This paper is devoted to Mongolic back borrowings of ultimate Turkic origin, which are numerous in Kyrgyz and focuses on certain phonetic criteria that facilitate the identification of back borrowings from Mongolic based on similar phonetic changes which such words have undergone.

It proposes to divide such borrowings into three main chronological groups: a) back borrowings of pre-Old Turkic origin; b) back-borrowings of Old Turkic origin and c) back borrowings of Early Middle Turkic origin.

Based on the findings of this paper, it is claimed that a great number of Mongolian elements in Kyrgyz, including back borrowings, can be explained by the long-lasting Turkic-Mongolian bilingualism in the Tien-Shan region that ultimately ended up in favor of Turkic, as well as a local Turkic-Mongolian sprachbund.

Key words: Turkic, Mongolic, Kyrgyz, language contact, back borrowing

1. Introduction

In the most straightforward description, back borrowings² are lexical items copied from a donor language into a recipient language that are later transferred back from the latter to the former in a different phonetic shape and often with different semantics. Back borrowings can be seen in many languages, but this phenomenon is especially noticeable in those that have centuries-old and in-depth contact with each other. Greco-Latin, Sino-Japanese, Perso-Arabic, or Franco-English language contacts generated many back borrowings that became textbook examples of how they (should) look like.

Just like these languages, Turkic and Mongolic languages also exhibit a great number of lexical correspondences and the issue of mutual borrowings between them

¹ Marie Skłodowska Curie Fellow, Department of Turcology, Institute for Slavic, Turkic and Circum-Baltic Studies, Johannes Gutenberg University of Mainz, Germany; e-mail: ralimov@uni-mainz.de, alimoff@gmail.com, ORCID: 0000-0002-5855-3594.

² There are different terms to denote the words that underwent such a process such as *reverse borrowing*, *re-borrowing*, *taken-back word*, *returned loan*, or even *false borrowing*, and all of them refer to the metaphors *borrowing* and *loan*. The most widespread term among them is *re-borrowing*, however, it is also used by some linguists for the linguistic items borrowed more than once by the same language, so just to avoid any ambiguity I would prefer here to use the term *back borrowing* which is equivalent to German *Rückentlehnung*.

has been discussed for many decades, both within frameworks of genetic and areal linguistics, respectively. However, the issue of back borrowings, which are found to varying degrees in many Turkic languages, has not been addressed within the context of Turkic-Mongolian contact, except in those cases where the authors only mentioned some examples in passing without paying special attention to this topic (see Shcherbak 1997, 1999; Schönig 2000: 15-16; Nagy 1996: 144-145; Khabtagaeva 2009: 267-271).

As a rule, back borrowings emerge when two languages co-exist for a long time, and the study of this phenomenon allows us to trace many features of mutual influences between contact languages, including the time of borrowing, certain phonetic forms, or semantic features that the borrowed words possessed or obtained in the process, as well as to better understand the phenomenon of borrowing in all its diversity.

In the case of the Turkic-Mongolian linguistic contact I would argue that back borrowings can also contribute to the discussion of the Turkic-Mongolian linguistic kinship, which can be said to have reached a dead end to some extent. It seems that they can play a role of a certain "litmus test" in identifying the ultimate origin of each of the Turkic-Mongolian lexical parallels because in order to reach a certain consensus on this issue researchers began to apply the principle of "apples and oranges separately" which was already proposed by A. Róna-Tas (1974: 31-45) in the 1970s.

According to this principle, to clarify the genetic relationship between the so-called Altaic, or at least between Turkic and Mongolian languages, one should first identify all early, intermediary, and late lexical items copied from the opposing language group in each of the given languages, and then analyse the residues to determine whether their similarity is owed to linguistic genetic affinity or again to mutual contacts.

The pieces of evidence attested in a variety of historical and linguistic sources show that contacts and interactions between the speakers of these two language groups have been most intense and continuous in contact zones of Siberia and Central Asia.

Among the Turkic languages Tuva and Yakut in Siberia as well as Kyrgyz and Kazakh in Central Asia had the most intensive and prolonged contact with the Mongolic languages judging by the number of Mongolian copies.

The presence of a large number of Mongolian elements of mainly Khalkha-Buryat origin in the Tuvan language, which can be chronologically attributed to the late layer is due to several factors such as living in a contact subarea, subordination to state formations controlled by the Mongols, accepting the Tibeto-Mongolian form of Buddhism, using Mongolian as a written language and, as a result, Tuvan-Mongolian asymmetric bilingualism in favour of the latter (see Tatarintsev 1976: 3-15; Khabtagaeva 2009: 21-25).

On the other hand, the loans of Mongolian origin in the Yakut language show that Yakuts had intense contact with Mongols during the empire of Genghis Khan and his successors (13-14th centuries), which is also the case for other Turkic languages, as well as during the Northern Yuan reign (15-16th centuries) when the ancestors of modern Yakuts were socially and politically subordinated to Mongols. S. Kałuziński, in his work *Mongolische Elemente in der jakutischen Sprache* (1962: 119-128) holds a two-fold opinion as to the source language; the first states that the Mongolian loanwords that have passed into Yakut originated from a Mongolic language that is no longer exists, and the second that all these loanwords were adopted at different times from different Mongolian languages as a result of centuries of contact, which seems more plausible and rational.

From the perspective of Turkic-Mongolian language contact, Kyrgyz and to a lesser extent Kazakh³ are unique in that they display not only simple vocabulary transfers represented by lexical borrowings which in can also be seen in other Turkic languages in varying degrees, but also linguistic items that can be described as consequences of the influence of the Mongolian superstrate, which is rarely the case for other Turkic languages.

Moreover, addition to explicit examples of both borrowing and superstrate interference, there are many cases where it is also difficult to determine whether a specific linguistic phenomenon must be attributed to contact borrowing or the influence of the substrate. The period of Kyrgyz-Mongolian language contact lasted for centuries, during which contact occurred at continually varying levels of intensity. Linguistic dominance also shifted back and forth between Mongolic languages and Kyrgyz. Thus, superstrate-related influences are intermingled with layers of borrowings.

II. Mongolian copies of Turkic Origin in Kyrgyz

Despite this complexity, there are a large number of lexical transfers of Mongolian origin in Kyrgyz that can be revealed and classified as back-borrowings from the etymological perspective.

At first glance, the identification of back borrowings of Turkic origin appears to be quite simple and for this, it seems enough to collect words of Turkic origin in works that refer to such borrowings in Mongolic languages that have undergone phonetic, morphological or semantic changes, and check whether they occur in one of these altered forms in Turkic languages, in our case, in Kyrgyz.

Indeed, the works by B. Vladimirtsov (1912), N. Poppe (1955), G. Clauson (1957, 1959, 1960, 1962, 1972), G. Doerfer (1963-1975), L. Clark (1980), V. Rassadin (1980, 2007), A. Shcherbak (2005), C. Schönig (2003, 2005), G. Kara (2001), V. Rybatzky (2011), O. Ünal (2016) and many other relevant studies contributed much to the study of Turkic borrowings in Mongolic languages and facilitated our task. However, there are also specific difficulties. First, the principles that determine which part of the Turkic-Mongolic parallel vocabulary belongs to Turkic and which to Mongolic have not been fully established. Secondly, these works do not cover all Turkic borrowings in Mongolic languages. Thirdly, they mainly analyse the linguistic evidence of historical languages from written historical sources and not the data of living modern languages.

Therefore, my task and main purpose here is not only to confirm the presence of Mongolian back borrowings in Kyrgyz but also to identify unrecorded or local back borrowings and to highlight specific, particularly phonetic criteria for their identification and thus draw attention to the potential of studies in this direction.

In order to identify these lexical transfers, I have been guided mainly by the phonological and etymological criteria described in the works of linguists such as G. Nemeth (1912a; 1912b; 1914), G. Clauson (1960), N. Poppe (1955, 1969), A. Rona-Tas (1974), L. Gerzenberg (1974), G. Doerfer (1963-1975) N. A. Syromjatnikov (1975), L. Clark 1980: 36-59, A. Shcherbak (1996: 199-203), V. Rassadin (1980: 103-107; 2007; 2008; 2014), É. Csáki (2006), B. Khabtagaeva (2009), É. Kincses-Nagy (2018) and others to distinguish both Turkic elements in Mongolian languages and, conversely, Mongolian elements in Turkic languages.

³ Although Kazakh and Kyrgyz share a significant number of the same Mongolian copies of different chronological layers, the former lacks the layer of Mongolic copies that is common for Kyrgyz (although mainly northern dialects) and Southern Siberian Turkic idioms. Here, I did not take into consideration the Kazakh variety spoken in the Bayan-Ölgii province of Mongolia, where the Mongolian-based contact-induced changes are still ongoing.

In summarising the previous works on the subject, V. Rybatski (2011: 185-202) distinguishes three main layers of Turkic borrowings in Mongolic. The first layer is of Bulghar Turkic origin and was copied until the 3-4 centuries AD; the second layer stems from the 9-13 centuries, and the third layer is of Turfan Uighur origin at the beginning of the Mongol expansion to the West from the 13th century.

Two more layers of Turkic loanwords can also be added here chronologically, the first from the 15th- to the 17th centuries and the second from the 18th- to the 20th centuries. They represent local Turkic loanwords in specific Mongolian languages, i.e. Turkic borrowings appeared at the expense of local (by scope) and short (in terms of time frame) linguistic contacts between speakers particular of Turkic and Mongolic languages, such as took place between Kazakh-Kyrgyz and Oirat-Kalmyk languages, between Western Kipchak idioms and Kalmyk, between Western Siberian Turkic and Buryat, between Tuva and Khalkha-Mongolian or between Kyrgyz and Sart-Kalmak as well as between Kazakh of Bayan-Ölgiy and Khalkha-Mongolian.

The situation is similar with the Turkic borrowings in Mongolian. Chronologically, the Mongolic back borrowings found in Kyrgyz can be divided into three main groups based on phonetic features and their development in the different periods of the Turkic language: a) back borrowings of pre-Old Turkic origin; b) back borrowings of Old Turkic origin and c) back-borrowings of Early Middle Turkic origin.

2. Back borrowings of pre-Old Turkic origin

Among the phonetic criteria for identifying the borrowings of Turkic origin that were copied into Mongolian in the pre-Old Turkic period, the following can be distinguished:

2.1. Proto-Turkic reduced stem-final vowels.

The stem-final vowels were gradually reduced and disappeared except for a few remnants and traces until Old Turkic, but remained in Turkic copies in Mongolian languages and are reflected in the back borrowings in Kyrgyz.

Kyrg. *juuru*- “to knead; to mix, stir” ← M, cf. MM (SH) *jūre*- H91, WMM (IM) *juğura*- P439, LM *juğura*- L1077b, *jūğura*- “to knead, mix” L1051a, HMog *зуурах*, Lu386b, Bur. *зуураха* Ch280b, Ojr. *зуураха* Tod167, Kalm *зуурх* Mn258b ← Turkic, probably PT **yoğurā*-, cf. OldT *yoğur*- “to knead (dough etc.)” C906a >> Kyrg. *juur*- “id.”.

Kyrg. *sura*- “to ask (a question); to inquire (about smth); to rule, govern; to ask in marriage” ← M, cf. MM (SH) *sura*- H137, LM *sura*- “to inquire, interrogate; to ask in marriage” L738b, HMog *сурax* Lu847b, Bur. *хураглаха* Ch663a, Ojr. *сурaxa* Tod303, Kalm *сурх* Mn463 ← Turkic, probably from PT **sōrā*-, cf. OldT *sor*- “to ask (a question); to inquire (about smth)” C843b-844a (see also Doerfer §1231).

Kyrg. *quča* “(male) lamb” ← M, cf. MM (HY) *quča* (M91), WMM (IM) *quča* “lamb” P445, (Muq). *quča* “ram” P307, LM *quča* “ram; uncastrated lamb”, L979a, HMog *хуц* Lu1419b, Bur. *хуца* Ch595b, Ojr. *хуца* Tod 417, Kalm *хуц* Mn. 616b ← Turkic, probably from PT **qōčā*, cf. OldT *qoč*, *qočnar*, *qočgar* “ram” C592ab, Kyrg. *qočqor* (see also Doerfer §1550);

Kyrg. *qira* “edge, rim; border mountain hollow; ridge, edge of a mountain” ← M, cf. MM (SH) *kija’ar*, *kiji’ar* H101, LM *kira* “summit or ridge of a mountain; small mountain chain; foothills; slope; a trip (usually of horn) attached to the front and rear edges of the saddle”, HMog *хяр* Lu1486a, Bur. *хяра* Ch634a, Ojr. *киле* “граница, рубеж” Tod198, Kalm *кир* “размер; мера; около, приблизительно, примерно” Mn301b ← Turkic, probably PT **qirā*, cf. OldT *qir* “an isolated mountain or block of mountains; edge” C641ab >> Kyrg. *qir*, *qiran* “id.” (see also Doerfer §1598).

Kyrg. *šīqa-* “to squeeze, compress; press” ← M, cf. MM (SH) *šīḡa-* H140, WMM (Muk.) *šīya-* P33a, *šīqa-* P335b, LM *siqa-*, *siḡa-* to press, squeeze, squash; to strain (by squeezing); to crowd; to oppress; to urge, force something upon somebody, to fatten for slaughter” L721a, L.699a, HMog *шахах* Lu1618a, Bur. *шахаха* Ch694b, Ojr. *шахаха* Tod452, Kalm *шахх* Mn668b ← Turkic, probably PT **siqǎ-*, cf. OldT *siq-* “to squeeze, press, compress” C804b.

Kyrg. *temene* “a large needle used for sewing leather and other stiff material” ← M, cf. MM (SH) *tebene* H147, LM *tebene* L790a, HMog *тэвнэ* Lu1019b, Bur. *тэбэнэ* Ch463b, Ojr. *темне*, *тевне* Tod322, Kalm *темн* Mn492b ← Turkic, probably PT **temeně*, cf. OldT *teben* “a large needle, packing needle” C507a >> Kyrg. (dial) *teven* Muk885, Kaz *тебен* J627b Trkm *темен* B627b, but Alt. *тебене* Chu662a, *темене* Chu667b.

2.2. Turkic-Mongolian rhotacism (primary rhotacism)

Proto-Bulgharic or Oguric */r/ (or */f/) is thought to have preserved the Pre-Turkic state of affairs as reflected in early Mongolic loans from Proto-Bulgharic Turkic, whereas in Common Turkic it developed into /z/. Cognates in Kyrgyz, where one of the pairs is a back borrowing, clearly show this development.

Kyrg. *añıraqay* “large fissure, cleft; having a large gap” < M, cf. LM *anggarqai* “crevice, cranny, fissure; gaping, having a gap; slightly open, ajar (as a door), HMog *ангархай* Lu249b, Bur. *ангархай* Ch56a, Ojr. *аңзаһар* Tod33, Kalm *аңххр* Mn45a, also LM *aḡurqai* “mine, shaft; hole, pit; source, beginning; secret or hidden place”, HMog *уурхай* Lu1126a, Bur. *уурхай* Ch.490a, Ojr. *уурхаа* Tod461, Kalm *уурха* Mn542b ← Turkic, probably PT **aḡir*, cf. OldT *aḡiz* “mouth (in an anatomic sense; the mouth (of a river)) or any sort of aperture” C98a >> Kyrg. *ooz* “id.”

Kyrg. *araan* “no definite meaning, a mouth-related word, e.g. *araanī ačiq* “insatiable, greedy”) < M, cf. MM *ariʾa*, LM *araḡa* (< **ariḡa*) “molar; canine tooth; tusk”, HMog *араа(н)* Lu259a, Bur. *араа(н)* Ch59b, Kalm *аран* Mn46b ← Turkic, probably PT **ariḡǎ*, cf. OldT *aziḡ* “large tooth or tusk; canine tooth, molar” C283a >> Kyrg. *azuu* “id.”

Kyrg. *qimīran* “boiled milk with water” ← M, cf. LM *kiram*, *kirm-a* “boiled milk diluted with water” L470b, HMog *хярам* Lu1486a, Ojr. *кумер* Tod199, Kalm *кумп* Mn301a, *kimrān* “gekochte kuhmilch mit wasser gemischt” (Ram281), ← Turkic, probably PT **qimir*, cf. OldT *qimīz* “fermented mare’s milk, koumiss” C629b >> Kyrg. *qimīz* “id.” (see also Doerfer §1550);

Kyrg. *sergek* “prudent, vigilant, alert” ← M, cf. LM *sergeg* “vigilant, alert, careful, cautious; sensitive” L690a, HMog *сэрээ* Lu879a, Kalm *sergg*, Bur. *hergeg* “vigilant, alert ← Turkic **ser-gek*, cf. OldT *sez-* “to feel, sense” >> Kyrg. *sez-* “id.”

Kyrg. *omuroo* “sternum, breastbone; horse chest” ← M, LM *omuruḡun*, *omuruu* “sternum, clavicle, breast; soft skin of animal’s neck; white hair on animal’s breast” L611ab, HMog. *омруу* “ключица; грудная кость; грудина, грудь (лошади, мула, птицы); отвислая кожа на груди (у рогатой скотины); белая шерсть на груди (у зверей)” Lu658a, Bur. *оморюу(н)* Ch369b, Ojr. *омруун* Tod260, Kalm. *омрун* Mn397b ← Turkic, probably PT **omuruḡ* (< *omru-* “to detach, disjoint (the bones) – (U)ḡ) → M **omurḡa* → OldT. *oḡurḡa* “backbone” C92b-93a >> Kyrg. *omurtqa*, TT. *omurḡa* “id.” and Kyrg. *omur-* “to detach, disjoint (the bones)”. Just like in the alternation in OldT. *sāmiz* ‘corpulent’ vs. OldT. *sāmri-* ‘to be or become corpulent’, OldT. *sekiz* ‘sharp-witted’ vs. OldT. *sekri-* ‘to jump, hop’, OldT. *yultuz* ‘star’ vs. *yultri-* ‘to gleam or shimmer’, OldT. *töz* ‘root, origin, element’ vs. OldT. *törö-* ‘to come into existence’ and OldT. *yaviz* ‘bad’ vs. OldT. *yavri-* ‘to be or become weak’ (see Erdal 2004: 84-85) the

noun form of PT **omru-* should be **omuz* as seen later in EMT *omuz* “top of the shoulder; upper arm” Boesch209a, Chag. *omuz* “épaule” DeC81 and TT. *omuz* “id.” Tekin’s claim (Tekin 1960:402-403) that TT. *omuz* ← Greek *ώμος* thus seems dubious.

2.3. Turkic-Mongolian lambdacism

As in the case of Turkic-Mongolian rhotacism, Proto-Turkic */l₂/ evolved into Common Turkic /š/ while in Proto-Bulgharic it was preserved. There are back borrowings of Turkic origin in Kyrgyz that reflect this situation.

Kyrg. *dalda* “shelter,; nook; shady spot” ← M cf. LM *dalda*, HMog *далд* Lu689a, Bur. *далда* Ch251b, Ojr. *далда* Tod113, Kalm *далд* Mn179b ← Turkic, probably PT **ḡal-*, cf. OldT *yaš-* “to hide, conceal” >> Kyrg. *jašir-* “id.”

Kyrg. *qolbu-* “to connect, link to; to come one after another” ← M, cf. MM (MA) *qolba-* (*qolbaba yamayi yamadu = qoşdi nemeni nemege* “присоединил вещь к вещи”) P301a, LM *qolba-* “to unite, combine, connect, incorporate; to link to; to unite in marriage” L957b, HMog *холбох* Lu1323a, Bur. *холбохо* Ch576a, Ojr. *холвоха* Tod400, Kalm *холөх* Mn593b ← Turkic, probably PT **qol-*, cf. OldT. *qoş-* “to conjoin, unite (two things)” C670b-671a >> Kyrg. *qoş-* “id.”

Kyrg. *sal, zalun* “youth, a young man”, *jaloon* “agile, alert, dexterous” ← M cf. **jalaḡun* (< *jal-A+gUn*), cf. MM (SH) *jala’ui* H85, LM *jalaḡu* “young, youthful; youth; youthfulness” L1029b, HMog *залуу* Lu343a, Bur. *залуу* Ch263a, Ojr. *залуу* Tod151, Kalm *залу* Mn238b ← Turkic, probably PT **jal*, cf. OldT *yaš* “fresh, moist” >> Kyrg. *jaš* “young, youthful; youth; fresh, moist”.

2.4. Changes affecting Turkic voiced dental spirant ḡ-

Proto-Turkic voiced dental spirant *ḡ* (or *d₂*) in the initial position which yielded *y* in Old Turkic becomes plosive /d/ in Mongolian (see Clauson 1959: 186). While back borrowings in Kyrgyz reflect the process of adaptation of the related words into Mongolian, their Turkic cognates in Kyrgyz reflect their evolution in the Turkic environment.

Kyrg. *daaqi* “spring wool (not yet faded); fig. rags, shreds” ← M, cf. LM *daḡaki* “snarl, tangle; combings of hair; shedding of hair; hair of child before cutting it for the first time”, HMog *даахь* Lu666b, Bur. *дааху* Ch195b (< **dawaki*) ← Turkic *ḡabaqu*, cf. OldT *yapaqu* “colt, flees wool” >> Kyrg. *jabaḡi* “molting; spring sheep wool”.

Kyrg. *daqı* short-sleeved calfskin jacket ← M, cf. LM *daqu* “coat with fur outside” L237b, HMog. *дах* LU707a, Bur. *даха* Ch707a, Ojr. *даха* Tod117, Kalm. *дах*^o (Ram72b ← Turkic *ḡaḡu*, cf. OldT *yaqu* (*yaḡqu*) “raincoat” C898b >> Alt. *jaqi* “coat with fur outside” Bask147b.

Kyrg. *dayin* “enemy, hostile” ← M, cf. MM (Muq) *dain* P138a, LM *dain* “war, battle; hostility, enmity”, HMog *дайн* Lu682b, Bur. *дай(н)* Ch199a, Ojr. *дәән* Tod119, Kalm *дән* Mn189b ← Turkic *ḡaḡi*, cf. OldT *yaḡi* “enemy, hostile; war” >> Kyrg. *joo* “id.”

Kyrg. *domoq* “story, tale; scandal, verbal onslaught” ← M, cf. MM (SH) *domoh+ci* “Schwätzer” H37, LM *domuḡ* “legend, fable; historical tale; joke, fun, ridicule” L261a, HMog *домоғ* Lu717b, Bur. *домоғ* Ch195a, Ojr. *дооғ* “насмешка, издёвка, шутка” Tod129, Kalm *домг* Mn206a ← Turkic, probably PT **domaḡ*, cf. MamK. *yomaq*, Kyrg. *jomog* (see further ESTJa IV/220-221).

Kyrg. *delbir* “smth. flattering” ← M, cf. MM *delbü-* (in *kei delbükü yama* “fan” P213b, LM *debi-*, *dele-* “to wave, flap (as wings); to fan” L238a, L248a, *debigür* (<*delbi-gür*) “any device used to produce wind” L238a, HMog *дэвүүр* LU774a, Bur. *дэбюур* Ch231b, Kalm. *dewüür* (Ram91a), Dag *дэлбур* “веер” Tum63 ← M, Turkic, probably PT *ḡelpi-*, cf. OldT *yelpi-* “to fan, wave a fan” C920a >> Kyrg. *jelpi-* “id.”

Kyrg. *tabarsıq* “bladder” ← M, cf. MM (Muq) *dabasun* P137a, LM *dabusang*, *dabasağ*, *dabusağ*, *dabisağ* “bladder; lower part of the abdomen, the pubic region (colloq.)” L. 213b, HMog *давсаг*, *давсан*, *давснаг*, Lu670b, 670b, 671a, Bur. (west dial.) *дабһаг* (ESMJa 162), Kalm *давса* Mn174a ← Turkic, probably PT **damuz*, cf. OldT *yamuz* “the groin” C940. Although considering the syllable-final *-r* seems tempting in terms of an alternation of *r-z* in Turkic, it seems more plausible that it is an epenthesis in Kyrgyz.

3. Back borrowings of Old Turkic origin

3.1. OldT intervocal *-d-* is preserved as plosive *-d-* in Mongolic, while in Kyrgyz it developed into *-y-*.

Kyrg. *ada(q)* “end, ending; completion; last, ultimate” ← M, LM *adağ* “end, finish; extremity, estuary, lower part or mouth of a river; last; extreme, farthest (as a frontier, limit, or region); the worst, of the lowest quality” L9; HMog. *адәг* Lu178a, Bur. *адәг* Ch31ab, Ojr. *адәг* Tod21, Kalm *адә* Mn27b ← OldT *adaq* “leg, foot” C45ab >> TT *ayak*, Kyrg. *ayaq* “leg, lower leg; end, bottom, lower part”.

Kyrg. *quduq* “draw well” ← M, cf. LM *quduğ* “id.”, HMog *хүдәг* Lu1394b, Bur. *хүдәг* Ch590a, Ojr. *хүдәг* Tod410, Kalm *хүдә* Mn607b ← OldT *quduğ* “id.” >> Kyrg. *quy(u)* hole, pit.

Kyrg. *sīdir-* “to scrape off, rip off” ← M, LM *sidur-* “to rise, stand, erect, straighten; to pull the reins by stretching the head forward or downward (of a horse)” L698a HMog *шудрах* (II) Lu1654b, Bur. *шударха* Ch702b, Ojr. *шударха* Tod461, Kalm *шудрх* Mn682a ← OldT *sīdir-* “to strip, peel, scrape and the like” >> Kyrg. *sīyir-* “id.”

3.2. OldT *sl-* > M *šl-*

Turkic does not allow /š/ in the initial position, whereas in Mongolic /š/ developed from *si* (> *šī*). Therefore, the words in Kyrgyz with the initial *š-* that have cognates in other Turkic languages with the initial *s-*, are considered back borrowings.

Kyrg. *šība-* “to smear, plaster” ← M, cf. MM *suba-*, *šiba-* “id.”, LM *siba-* “to plaster, stucco; to apply mud; to apply ointment; to cover or gather thickly on something (as insects)”, HMog *шавах* Lu1596a, Bur. *шаваха* Ch. 683b, Ojr. *шаваха* Tod446, Kalm *шаврмх* Mn659b ← Turkic, probably **sī:ba-*, cf. OldT *suva-* “to plaster” C785a >> TT. *sīva-* “id.”, Kyrg. *sīypa-* “put or spread (something) on a surface”.

Kyrg. *šīpirgī* “broom, besom” ← M, cf. MM *šīürgü* “id.”, LM *sigür* “broom, whisk broom; filter, strainer; fine comb”, HMog *шүүр* Lu1667b, Bur. *шүүр* “сито, решето для процеживания; фильтр” Ch708b, Ojr. *шүүрүүл* Tod465, Kalm *шүүр* “сито, решето; фильтр” Mn686b ← OldT *sūpürgü* (*sipirgü*) “broom, brush” C792a >> TT. *sūpürge* “broom, whisk”.

Kyrg. *šīri-* “to quilt, stitch, lace” ← M, cf. LM *širi-* “to quilt, stitch” L717b, HMog *шурэх*, Bur. ← OldT *sīri-* “to quilt or smock (a garment)” C845a >> TT *sīri-* “id.”

Kyrg. *šīriq* “pole” ← M, cf. LM *siruğ* “pole, long mast, stake” L718b, HMog. *шурәг* Lu1658b, Ojr. *шурәг* Tod464, Kalm *шурәг* Mn684b ← OldT. *sīruq* “pole; tentpole” C848ab >> TT *sīrik* “id.”

Kyrg. *šimir-* “to drink without taking a breath, suck, sip; to absorb” ← M, LM. *simili-* to stroke; to sip, suck” L710a, HMog *шумэх* Lu1631a, Ojr. *шумехе* Tod455, Kalm *шумх* Mn675b ← OldT *simür-* to swallow in a single gulp” C829b-830a >> TT *sömür-* “id.”

Kyrg. *šumqar* “falcon” ← M **siṅqor* cf. LM *šongqur*, HMog *шонхор* Lu1645a, Bur. *шонхор* Ch699b, Ojr. *шонхор* Tod459, Kalm *шонхр* Mn679b ← OldT *siṅqur* “a bird of prey, the gerfalcon, *Falco gyrfalco*” C838a >> TT *sungur* “id.”

The palatalization also affects stem-internal /s/ before /i/.

Kyrg. *ašiq* “in excess; surplus; exceeding, surpassing” ← M, cf. LM *asiġ* “profit, gain; benefit, advantage” L57a, HMog. *awuə* Lu339b, Bur. *awaa* (I) Ch74a, Ojr. *awuə* Tod43, Kalm. *aw* Mn59b ← OldT *asiġ* “profit, advantage” C244b (see also Doerfer II, §480).

Kyrg. *tepši* “washtub” ← M, cf. MM *tebšin*, LM *tebsi*, HMog *məwū* Lu1021a, Bur. *məwə* Ch463b, Ojr. *məwū* Tod320, Kalm *məwū* Mn488a ← OldT *tebsi*, *tevsi* (← Chin. 碟子 *die zi* “bowl, plate”) >> TT. *tepsi* “tray”.

3.3. OldT -č and -š > M -s

Mongolian does not have voiceless affricate and spirant consonants in the final position, therefore Turkic -č and -š alters to -s. Thus, those Mongolian copies in Kyrgyz that have cognates in Turkic with the final -č or -š are considered back borrowings.

Kyrg. *adis* “approach, method; behaviour; dexterous, skilful; specialist” ← M, LM. *adis* “blessing, benediction; consecration, bestowal of miraculous power by deity; panacea; smallpox (euph(emism))” L11a, *adistai*, *adistu* “blessed, consecrated, blissful” L11a, HMog. *ađuc* Lu86a, Bur. *ađuc* Ch32b, Ojr. *əđuc* Tod46, Kalm. *əđc* Mn65a (< *adišdid*, *adištid*, *adiš*) ← M, OldT. *adištīt* “magische Kraft, magische Kontrolle, magische Ermächtigung, (im religiösen Sinne) Anleitung, Direktive || *büyü gücü*, *büyü ile kontrol etme*, *büyü ile yetki*, *büyü ile yetkili kılma* (dinî anlamda) *talimat*” ← TochB *adhištīt* ← Skt. *adhištīta* (see W13a, Kara 2001: 78).

Kyrg. *ilbirs* “snow leopard” ← M, LM *irbis* “panther, leopard” L413b, HMog. *upəəs* Lu428b, Bur. *əpəəd* Ch734b, Ojr. *upəec* Tod176, Kalm. *irws* Ram210a ← OldT *irbič*, *irbiš* “the Siberian panther, *Felis irbis*” C198b-199a >> Tuv. *irbiš* “барс” Ten210a.

Kyrg. *jel moġuz*, *jel moġus* “monster, mythical creature” ← M, cf. MM (SH) *mangġus*, *mangħus* “Dschlungenschlange, Riesenschlange”, HMog. *мангас*, *мангус* “сказочное чудовище” Lu475a, Ojr. *маңгас* (*маңгус*) Tod.226, Kalm. *mūs* (< *muġus* “irgendwelche riesen mit übernatürlichen kräften; die magier Ram269b (< **maġuš*) ← OldT *moġoč* “Magier, (c) einer der heiligen drei Könige || *muġ*, *kutsal üç kraldan biri* W477b cf. Alt. *моңыс* “чудовище, чудище” Chum474b. (See Ram269b, but Clark (1980: 45) offers different etymology, since the difficulty lies in the too great semantic difference between OldT. *moġoč* and HMog. *мангас*, *мангус* (Kara 2001: 101)).

Kyrg. *tos-* “to receive; to encounter, meet someone who is coming; to catch something moving toward the subject” ← M, LM *tos-*, HMog *мосох* Lu965a, Orj. *мосха* Tod334, Kalm *мосх* Mn509a ← OldT *tuš-* “to meet and the like” C560a. LM *todqar* “obstacle, obstruction, impediment; evil, calamity; demon, evil spirit” L813 reflects further intra-Mongol -s > -d change which will be discussed below.

Kyrg. *ulut* “nation; people” ← M, LM *ulus* “people, nation; country, state; empire, dynasty”, HMog *улс* Lu1073b, Bur. *улад* Ch487b, *улас* Ch479b”, Ojr. *улас* Tod352, Kalm *улс* Mn532a ← OldT *uluš* “people, nation”. While *ulus* in many historical and modern Turkic languages was back borrowed from the MM period (for more details see Räsänen 513a, ESTJa I/592), its cognate with final -t in Kyrgyz, Kazakh, and Karakalpak is a remnant from either a Buryat-type Mongolic language or of the language of the Jalair tribe which later was Turkicized and incorporated into these nations since both in modern Buryat and the idiom of the Jalait-Dürbet in Inner Mongolia Old Mongolic -s becomes -d (Svantesson et al. 2005: 204; Todayeva 1981: 214).

3.4. Old -CC > M -CCV

Turkic words with final consonant clusters such as *-rt, -lt, -lp, -nt, -nč, -st, -rk* were copied into Mongolian in the form of CCV due to the phonotactic limitations of the latter. (e.g., T *qilinč* “deed” > M *kilinče/qilinča* “sin”; see also Clauson 1959: 184, Clark 1980: 43).

The back borrowings in Kyrgyz that serve as an example of this phonetic feature of Mongolian are as follows:

Kyrg. *bulǵu-* “to make jerky movements” ← M, LM. *bulǵul-, bulǵal-* “to disjoint, luxate; to break at the root, knock out of a socket” L134b, HMog. *булгалах* “вывернуть, вывихнуть, сломать в суставе; выламывать (напр. кость при разделке туши)” Lu432b, Bur. *булгалха* Ch122a, Ojr. *булгалха* Tod79, Kalm. *булхрх* Mun118a ← OldT **burq-* “to be wrinkled” C360ab >> TT. *burk-* “to wrench, sprain”.

Kyrg. *erke* “spoiled, pampered; coddle” ← M, MM (SH) *erke* “Macht, Majestät” H45, LM *erke* “self-willed, willed, wilful, wayward, capricious; spoiled (of children); wilfulness, waywardness, capriciousness” L329a, HMog *эрх* (I) and (II) Lu1720b-1721ab. Bur. *эрхэ* (I) and (II) Ch737a, Ojr. *эрке* (I) and (II) Tod479, Kalm. *эрк* (I) and (II) ← OldT. *erk* “authority; free will, independence” >> Kyrg. *erk* “id.”. Although ESTJa I/296-297 proposes an etymological explanation of *erke* on the basis of Turkic, Clauson suggestion that it is an early loanword in Mongolian seems to be more realistic. The first meaning in all Mongolic languages is related to “authority; power; free will”, while the second registered in LM seems due to its semantic extension.

Kyrg. *janči-* “to crush, fraction” ← M, LM *janči-, nanči-, jangči-* “to beat, hit; to punish by hitting with rods or a whip; to thrash, whip” L1034a, HMog *жанчих* Lu289b, *занчих* Lu350a, Bur. *наншаха* Ch338a, Kalm *нанчх* 368b ← probably *ǰ*-type OldT. *janč-*, cf. OldT *janč-* “to crush, trample on” C944b, *sanč-* “to pierce (with a lance), transfix” C835b >> Kyrg. *janč-* “id.”.

Kyrg. *kenje* “the youngest child” ← M, cf. LM *kenje*, aftermath, rowen; late-grown crop; child born to old parents; weak child”, HMog *хэнз* Lu1466b, Bur. *хэнзэ* Ch628a, Ojr. *кензе* Tod193, Kalm *кенз* Mn 294a ← OldT *kenč* “the young (of human beings or animals); child” C727b >> TT *genç* “young”.

Kyrg. *kerči-, kerče-* “to make a notch, cut; to chop off, chop” Muk500b ← M, cf. LM *kerči-* “to cut, mince, slice, carve; to make incisions, notch”, HMog. *хэрчих* Lu1469a, Bur. *хэршэхэ* Ch629b, Ojr. *керчихе* Tod195, Kalm. *керчх* Mn296b ← OldT. *kert-* “to gash, cut a notch in smth.” C738b >> Kyrg. *kert-* “id.”

Kyrg. *süŋgü-, šumqu-, čumqu-* “to dive, plunge” ← M, cf. LM *singǵu-, šungǵu-* “to dive, plunge; to wade in water” L711b, HMog *шунгах* Lu1657b, Bur *шунгах* Ch703b, Ojr *шумбаха* Tod462, Kalm *šung^oхр* (Ram368a) ← OldT *siŋ-* “to sink into smth.; to be absorbed, digested” C833b >> Alt. *чөң-* “нырять; окуна́ться, погружа́ться” Chum835a, Tuv. *шымын-* “id.” Ten558a.

Kyrg. *ürgü-* “to stumble, to almost fall; to shy, dash aside” ← M, cf. LM *ürge-, ürgü-, ürege-* “to be(come) alarmed or frightened” L1012a, HMog *үрээх* Lu1186a, Bur *үрээхэ* Ch515b, Ojr *үрээхе* Tod369, Kalm *үрэх* mn554a ← Turkic, probably OldT *ürk-* “to be startled, scared, frightened” C221a >> Kyrg. *ürk-* “id.”

3.5. OldT *tl-* > M *či-*

It is well known that *t* in Mongolian does not occur before *i* (or **i*) and in this position, it became *č*. Turkic copies that contain *tl-* also became *či-* during their adaptation. This sound changes *di-/ti-* > *ji-/či-* appears in Mongolian in the 11th century (Schönig 2005: 150). However, there is an interesting note left by Rashid ad-Din, a 13th-century author, also mentioned by C. Schönig, who records the following: “...their ruler's name was Qadir Buyuruq Khan (*qad'ir* means mighty conqueror). Since the

Mongols don't know this word, they call him Qajir Khan. Today, there is a certain Mongolian medicine called *qajir*, although anciently its name was *qadir*, meaning "powerful medicine" (Thackston 1998: 70). Schönig admits the possibility that the author was only thinking of the Turkic word form *qadir*, however the adaptation of the former personal name into Mongolian shows that this sound change was still ongoing during the 13th-century.

Kyrg. *aarči-* "to wipe, clean or dry by rubbing; to peel" ← M cf. MM *arči-*, LM *arči-* "to wipe, clean or dry by rubbing; to erase; to weed", HMog *арчих* Lu307b, Bur. *аршаха* Ch67a, Ojr. *арчуха* Tod39, Kalm *арчх* Mn52b ← (**arti-* <) OldT *arīt-* "to clean, purify (smth.)" >> TT. *arīt-* "to cleanse, purify (smth.)".

Kyrg. *čičira-* "to tremble, shake, shiver, quake" ← M cf. MM *čičire-* "to tremble, shake, shiver, quake; to quiver", LM *čičire-*, *čečere-*, HMog *чичрэх* Lu1585a, Ojr. *чичирехе* Tod443, Kalm *чичрх* Mn654a ← OldT *titre-* "to tremble, shake, quiver" >> TT. *titre-*, Kyrg. *titire-* "id."

Kyrg. *qayči* "scissors" ← M cf. MM *qaiči* "id." ← (**qağiti* < **qabiči* <), HMog *хайч(ун)* Lu1231a, Bur. *хайша* Ch538b, Oj. *хөөчу* Tod395, Kalm *хөөч* Mn587b ← OldT **qapiti*, cf. OldT *qiftu* C582a, EMT *qiftu*, *qipti* Boesch247a, KBalk. *кыпты* TenS445b, Khak. *хыпты* BasInk300a (see also Doerfer I §318)

Kyrg. *eerči-* "to take (someone) with one; allow (him) to follow one" ← M, **erči-* ← OldT *ert-* (causative of *er-*) C202a >> Kaz. *ert-* "to take (someone) with one; allow (him) to follow one" J179b, Yak. *irdää-* "исследовать, испытывать, изыскивать; следить, выслеживать, разыскивать след" Pek954-955.

Kyrg. *šišek* "a two-year-old castrated ram" ← M, MM (SH) *šilegü* (deaffrication of the initial *č-* after *ti->či-* probably happened in a later period); *šilegü honin* "zweijähriges Schaf" H140, cf. OldT *tišek* "a two-year-old sheep" (< *tiše-k*) C563b, cf. TT *şıšek* "sheep". Clauson correctly mentions *šilegü* as an early period Turkic copy in Mongolian, but in the case of *šišek* in Kyrgyz and other Turkic languages it can be assumed that this word as **tišek* was borrowed again by Mongolian from OldT and borrowed back to Turkic, although the later Mongolic form is not documented in historical sources.

3.6. OldT *dl-* > M *ji-*

As in the case with *t* before *i* (or **i*), Mongolian does not have *d* before *i* (or **i*) and when this is the case it became *ji* as a rule. Turkic copies that contain *dl-* also became *ji-* during their adaptation. There are quite a number of back borrowings in Kyrgyz that reflect this phonetic change some of which are given below.

Kyrg. *ajira-* "to separate, part; to be deprived" ← M cf. MM (SH) *ajiraḥu* "heimkehren, sich trennen" H4a, LM (with further with semantic extension) *ajira-* "to proceed, be take oneself; to sojourn; to retreat from (of exalted persons)" L62b and (seemingly with epenthesis) *anggjira-* "to detach oneself; to separate from; to become free from; to leave" L45a, HMog. *ангжрах* Lu251b, Bur. *анжарха* "замечать, примечать; видеть; понимать" Ch57b, *аңзарха* "потрескаться, рассыпаться" Tod33, Kalm. *ажлх* "наблюдать, приглядываться; замечать, примечать, подмечать" ← M, cf. OldT. *adīr-* "to separate (two things); to distinguish (between two things); to single out (prefer smth.)" C66b >> Kyrg. *ayir-*, *ayri-* "id."

Kyrg. *qajir*, *kejir* "stubborn; determined, courageous; hardened (of a person)" ← M cf. MM "mighty, powerful", LM *qajir* "id." HMog *хажур* Lu1223a, Bur. *хажар* Ch535a, Ojr. Kalm *хадяр* Mn567a ← OldT *qadir* "grim, brutal, oppressive, dangerous" C603b, cf. Khak. *хазыр* BasInk264b, Tuv. *кадыр* "крутой, отвесный; круча, крутизна" Ten217a.

Kyrg. *kejiġe* “nape, back of the head” ← M, cf. LM *gejiġe* “nape of the neck, plait or braid of hari, pigtail, queue; hair in general”, *gede* “nape or back of the neck, occiput” + GAn (a denominal noun suffix), HМог *эззээ* “коса, косички” Lu649b, Bur. *эззээ* Ch186b, Ojr. *зижуг* “затылок; коса” Ojr. Tod93, Kalm *зижэ* 142b ← PT **keđi*, cf. OldT *keđin* “behind (usually of place, less often of time; afterwards” C704b, cf. Kyrg. *kiyin* “afterwards”.

Kyrg. *kejim* “saddle blanket, caparison” ← M, cf. LM *kejim* “caparison, saddle cloth” L462b, HМог *хэжим* Lu1451b, Bur. *хэжэм* Shag514a, Kalm. *кэжм* Mn288b ← OldT. *kedim* “garment, clothes” C704a >> Kyrg. *kiyim* “id.”

3.7. OldT *ǰ-* = M *ǰ-*

Clauson (1959: 174-187) argues that all Turkic loans with initial *ǰ-* in Mongolian are from an Old Turkic dialect presumably spoken by the ancestors of the modern South Siberian dialects (“languages”) like Khakas, Mountain Altai, Tuvan, and the rest. Among the Mongolian vocabulary of *Muqqadimat al-Adab*, there are Turkic words both with the initial *y-* and *ǰ-*, which, according to Poppe (1938:53), were copied from different Turkic varieties and the latter, in his opinion, also from the *ǰ*-type Turkic language and as Poppe presumes of like Kazakh. LM *ǰanči-* and its variant *nanči-* as copies from Turkic, mentioned earlier clearly indicate that the Mongolian tribes had contact not only with speakers of the *ǰ*-type of Turkic languages, but with those South Siberian Turkic tribes whose languages are characterized by the regressive assimilation of *ǰ->n-* after the nasal sonorous consonants *n, m, ŋ*.

It appears that *ǰ*-type Turkic speakers were in contact with the Mongols prior to their westward expansion in the 13th century, since all borrowings with initial *ǰ-* are common to most Mongolian languages, i.e., they were copied before the breakup of the common Mongolian language.

As back borrowings from Mongolian of the *ǰ*-type Turkic language, we can mention those given below.

Kyrg. *ǰaŋtay* “having a certain feature”, *ǰaġday* “condition, position; circumstances” ← M, LM *ǰaŋtai* “having a certain habit or character; having a temper” L1036b (< *ǰaŋ* “character, nature; disposition, temperament; custom, habit, conduct” + *tai*) L1036, HМог *зантай (I)* Lu349b, Bur. *зантай* Ch265b, Kalm *занта* Mn241a ← probably *ǰ*-type OldT. **ǰaŋ*- cf. OldT *yaŋ* “pattern, model, kind, sort, manner; character, habit, disposition; pattern” ← Ch. 樣 *yàng* C940b) >> Alt. *jaŋ* (III) Chum185, Tuv *чаң* Ten516b.

Kyrg. *ǰaydaq* “without a saddle; unsaddled” ← M, LM *ǰaidang* “without a saddle; unsaddled”, HМог *зайдан(э)* Lu 337a, Bur. *зайдан* Ch260a, Ojr. *зөөдөң* Tod154, Kalm *зөөдң* Mn243b ← probably *ǰ*-type OldT. **ǰabīdaq*, cf. OldT *yabītaq* “(of a horse) bare-backed, not saddled” C873a, Khak. *чабдах* Baslnk304b

Kyrg. *ǰerdik* “wild; one who lives in solitude” ← M, cf. LM *ǰerlig* “wild, living or growing in a state of nature; savage; stray” L1046b, HМог *зэрлэе* Lu401a, Bur. *зэрлиг* Ch290b, Ojr. *зерлеэ* Tod158, Kalm *зерлэ* Mn248b ← probably *ǰ*-type OldT. **ǰerlig*, cf. OldT *yér* “ground, earth, land, soil, place” C954a + llġ > TT. *yerli* “local, indigenous”.

Kyrg. *ǰīloo*, *ǰoloov* “halter, reins” ← M, cf. LM *ǰīluġ-a* “reins” L1055a, HМог. *жолоо(н)* Lu316b-317a, Bur. *жолоо (II)* Ch248b, Ojr. *жолла* Tod145, Kalm. *жолла* Mn231b ← T, probably *ǰ*-type OldT. **ǰular*, cf. OldT *yular* “halter” C932a >> TT. *yular*, Tuv. *чулар* Ten546b.

Kyrg. *ǰoltoy* (or *aq ǰoltoy*) “lucky, fortunate” ← M., cf. LM *ǰoltai* lucky, fortunate Lessing 1070b (*ǰol* “good luck, fortune; good result, success” + *tai*), HМог *золтой*

Lu364a, Bur *золто(ў)* Ch271a. M *ʃol* ← probably *ʃ*-type OldT. **ʃol*, cf. OldT *yoł* “road, way” C917ab >> Kyrg. *ʃol* “id.”

Kyrg. *ʃumuy-* “to clench (the fist), to shut (mouth); to shrink”, *ʃimiy-* “to smile pursing lips” ← M, MM *ʃumuyi-* “to clench (the fist; to shrink)” ← probably *ʃ*-type OldT. **ʃum-*, cf. OldT *yum-* “to shut, usually the eyes, but also the mouth; to clench (the fist) C934a, Kyrg. *ʃum-* “id.”

3.8. Changes affecting OldT. postvocalic and intervocalic /g/

The reflex of OldT. *-aǰ* is *-oo* in Kyrgyz as can be seen in, e.g., OldT. *baǰ* “bond, link, tie” >> Kyrg. *boo*, OldT. *taǰ* “mountain” >> Kyrg. *too*, OldT. *saǰ* “alive” >> Kyrg. *soo*”, however there are some words that do not follow this rule, e.g., Kyrg. *saa-* “to milk”, cf. OldT *saǰ-* “id.”, Kyrg. *ʃaa-* “to rain; to snow”, cf. OldT *yaǰ-* “id.” Although as in the case of Kyrg. *ʃaa-* there is no attested Mongolic cognates, the words in Kyrgyz that give *-aǰ* > *-aa* just like in early Turkic copies in Mongolian should be considered as Mongolic back borrowings, e.g., MM (SH) *sa’ahu* “melken” H130, LM *saǰa-* L656a, HMog. *caax* Lu767a, Kalm. *caax* Mn434b ← OldT *saǰ-* C804b).

OldT. *-Vǰ* before *i* changes into a diphthong in Mongolic which is also reflected in back borrowings in Kyrgyz, e.g., Kyrg. *ayil*, *əyil* “settlement, village” ← M, cf. MM (SH) *ayil* H11, LM. *ail* L20a, HMog. *ayıl* Lu197a, Bur. *ayıl* Ch39a, Ojr. *əәл* Tod44, Kalm. *əәл* Mn61b ← OldT *aǰil* “an enclosure for livestock; cattle-pen, sheepfold; a settlement; a group of tents” C83b, cf. Kyrg. (dial.) *aǰil* “corral; (sheep) pen” (< probably through Uyghur or Uzbek).

Kyrg. *bayla-* “to tie in bunches, to pack, wrap” ← M, cf. *baǰla-* “to tie in bunches, bundles, sheaves or wisps; to pack, wrap” L69b, HMog. *baǰлах* Lu365b, Bur. *баглаха* Ch80a, Ojr. *баглаха* Tod50, Kalm. *багльх* Mn73b ← OldT *baǰla-* “to tie, fasten” C314b, cf. Kyrg. *boolo-* “id”. Even though Mongolic form in modern languages is also *baǰla-*, KBalk. *байла-* “id”. TenS113b makes us think that Kyrg. and KBalk. forms come from not yet attested MM **baǰila-*.

Kyrg. *čiyraq* “strong, hardy; dexterous” ← M, cf. MM (HY) *čī’iraǰ*, *čiyiraǰ* “dur, solide, vrai” Lew26, LM *čigiraǰ* “strong, robust, powerful; massive, solid; vigorous” L179b, HMog *чуйрәэ* Lu1577a, Bur. *шуйрәэ* Ch696b, Ojr. *чуиреэ* Tod439, Kalm *чуирәэ* Mn648a ← OldT *tīǰraq* “firm, tough and the like” (< OldT *tīǰra-q*) C471b.

Kyrg. *šiyraq* “shinbone, tibia” ← M, cf. LM *sigir-a*, *siger-e* shank, leg (of animals); hoof; fork on which the gun rests when firing” L702b, HMog. *шуйр* Lu1625b, Bur. *шуйра* Ch696b, Ojr. *шуйр* Tod454, Kalm. *шуйр* Mn671b ← OldT *sīǰra* “ravine, valley” C815b, EMT *sīǰraq* “the space between two fingers” Boesch289a, Chag. *sīǰraq* “cruche à goulot; coupe; tibia du bœuf” DeC368.

Kyrg. *tüydök* “ball or spindle of thread; cluster; ball of dust” ← M, cf. Lm *tegüdeg*, *tügüdeg* “ear of grain; bundle of cotton; cluster; ball or spindle of thread”, L795a, HMog. *түүдээ* (III) Lu1016b, Ojr. *түүдээ* Tod347, Kalm. *түүдэ* Mn525a ← OldT *tüg-* “to tie (a knot); to knot (a string)” C477a >> Kyrg. *tüy-* “id.”

In some cases, instead of expected OldT. *-aǰ* >> Kyrg. *-oo* it can be witnessed postvocalic devoicing of /g/ which is the case in Turkic copies in Mongolic. Mongolic forms later were transferred to Kyrgyz and gave rise to of etymological doublets such as in:

Kyrg. *inaq* “close friend; beloved; affection” ← M, cf. MM (SH) *inah* “Favorit, Günstling” H82, LM *inaǰ* “beloved, darling; favourite; lover; friend; benevolence, affection” L409b, HMog. *янаэ* Lu1757b, Bur. *инаэ* Ch294a, Ojr. *инәэ* Tod175, Kalm. *иньэ* Mn271b ← OldT *inaǰ* “intimate friend, confidant; (royal) favourite” (<OldT *ina-ǰ*) C182b.

Kyrg. *suraq* “id.” ← M., cf. MM (SH) *suraḡu* H137, LM *suraḡ, suruḡ* “news, rumor, information” L738b, HMog. *сyраэ* 846b, Bur. *hypae* Ch662b, Ojr. *сyраэ* Tod302, Kalm. *sur^uḡ* Ram338a, ← OldT *suruḡ* “question, inquiry” C848b >> Kyrg. *suroo* “question, interrogation, inquiry”.

Kyrg. *uruq* “seed, descendants, clan” ← M, cf. MM (SH) *uruh* H167, LM *uruḡ* “relatives by marriage; foetus” L885b, HMog. *ypae* “родственник, родня; свойственник (по жене); потомок, отпрыск данного рода, родной, сородич” Lu1088b, Bur. *ypae* Ch482b, Ojr. *ypae* Tod385, Kalm. *ur^uḡ* Ram451a ← OldT. *uruḡ* “seed, pip, kernel; progeny, descendants, clan” C214b >> Kyrg. *uruu* “relatives, clan”.

Kyrg. *külüg* “a good horse, race horse” ← M, MM (SH) *küluk* “Held, Recke” H105, LM *külüg, kölüḡ* a strong and swift horse” L501a, HMog. *хүлээ* Lu1425b, Bur. *хүлээ* Ch609a, Ojr. *күлээ* Tod214, Kalm. *күлэ* “*витязь, богатырь, батырь*” Mn324a ← OldT. *külüg* “famous” (< *kü* “rumour, name, reputation”) >> Kyrg. *küülüü* “smth. serviceable, in perfect order; in good condition”, cf. M → Uyg. *külüg* “a race horse”, Kaz. *külük* “id.”

The reflex of OldT. *-oḡu* is *-uu* in Kyrgyz as can be seen in, e.g., OldT *boḡum* “tie, bond” >> Kyrg. *buum* “id.”, OldT *qoḡuṣ* “groove” >> Kyrg. *quuṣ* “tight, narrow; gorge”, OldT *oḡul* “offspring, (male) child” >> Kyrg. *uul* “son” etc., while Mongolic back borrowings reflect the Mongolic type of secondary vowel length as in:

Kyrg. *boom* “narrow mountain pass, gorge” ← M, cf. LM *boḡum* “high and steep promontory, narrow mountain pass or valley”, HMog. *боом* “*мыс, выдающаяся скала*” Lu413a, Bur. *боомо* Ch114a, Ojr. *боодаг* “сноп, связка” Tod71, Kalm. *боом* “труднопроходимый, узкий проход” Mn109b ← OldT *boḡim, boḡum* “joint, or articulation; knot (in a stalk, etc.)” C315b >> Kyrg. *buum* “joint, bunch”.

Kyrg. *booz, boos* “pregnant (of animals)” < M, cf. LM *boḡus* “embryo, foetus; pregnant (of animals)” L113a, HMog. *боос* Lu414a, Bur. *боод* Ch113b, Kalm. *Боос* Mn109b < OldT *boḡuz, boḡoz* “throat” C322a, EMT *boḡaz* “pregnant” Boesch89a, cf. OldT *boḡuz+la-* >> Kyrg. *muuzda-* “to cut one's throat; to slaughter, sacrifice”.

3.9. OldT *t-* > Mong *d-*

In some cases, the initial *t-* in OldT words becomes voiced during their adaptation in Mongolic. This usually happens when the next consonant after the initial *t-* is one of the sonorants. Back borrowings in Kyrgyz reflect the phonetic shape of the respective words in Mongolic.

Kyrg. *dalay* “in great number or quantity, well enough” ← M, cf. MM (SH) *dalai* H31, LM. *dalai* “ocean, sea, great lake; much, many, in great number or quantity, universal, great (obs.)” L224a, HMog. *далай* Lu686ab, Bur. *далай* Ch200a, Ojr. *далаа* “много, множество; бесчисленный”, Kalm. *дала* ← OldT. *taluy* “sea, large body of water” C502ab.

Kyrg. *darhan* “blacksmith, gunsmith; honourable, respected” ← M, cf. LM. *darqan* “artisan, craftsman; person free from taxes and official duties; area or place set aside for religious reasons and therefore inviolable; sacred; great, celebrated” L236a; HMog. *дархан* Lu705a, Bur. *дарха(н)* Ch206b, Ojr. *дархан* Tod117, Kalm. *дархн* “мастер, кузнец, столяр” Mn185b ← OldT. *tarqan* “a high administrative title” C539b (see also Doerfer II §879).

Kyrg. *döḡkö, döḡgöč, döḡköč* “wood block, log, stump” ← M, cf. LM *dönngē* “cangue, heavy wooden collar worn around neck by convicts, shackles, fetters, irons, stocks (for criminals)”, HMog *дөнгө* Lu730 ← OldT *töḡörge* “a tree trunk” C525, but the original form is *töḡürge* “(hölzerner) Strafblock || (tahtadan) ceza bloḡu; Baumstumpf || ağaç kütüḡü, omaca” W738a.

Kyrg. *dala, talaa* “steppe, treeless plain” ← M, cf. LM. *tal-a* “plain, level space, steppe” L771a, HMog *тал* Lu904b, Bur *тала* Ch424b, Ojr *тала* Tod310, Kalm *тала* 473b ← OldT *tariġlaġ* “a cultivated field” C541b.

3.10. OldT č- > M š-

Despite the fact that č- in Mongolian can occur in all syllable-initial positions in some copies from Turkic deaffrication can happen.

Kyrg. *köksün* “old man; old woman” ← M, cf. LM *kögsin* “old (of men and animals) old man; old woman” L481a, HMog *хөгшин* Lu1358a, Ojr *көгшин* Tod204, Kalm *көгшин* Mn311a ← OldT *kökčün* “blueish, grey-beard” C710a.

Kyrg. *köršü* “neighbour” ← M, MM (IM) *körši* “neighbor” P440b, LM *körsi* L490b, HMog *хөрш* Lu1381a, Bur. *хүршэ* Ch615a, Ojr *көрши* Tod211, Kalm ← OldT *körši* “neighbor” (< probably *kör-(ü)š* “to see each other” +čl, although Erdal suggests *kör-üş-i* (OTWF § 3.118). Kazakh *körši* suggests it is a back borrowing since it would have been expected as *körsi* if it had derived from Old Turkic (for more details see Ölmez 2019: 268-276).

Kyrg. *šalbaa* “meadow” ← M, cf. LM *šalbaġ*, HMog Bur. *šalbaaġ* “лу́жа; пруд; илистая вода” Lu1602b, Bur *шалбааг* Ch686b, Kalm *шалва* Mn661b ← OldT *čalpaq* “dirt, filth”, *čalpaġ* “liquid mud” C418ab

Kyrg. *šiltoo* “reason, pretext, excuse” ← M, MM (SH) *šiltah, šilta’a* H140, (MA) *šiltaq* P333, LM *siltaġ* “cause, motive or reason, pretext; trick, ruse, stratagem” L707b, HMog *шалмаг* Lu1606a, Bur *шалмаг* Ch687b, Ojr *шалмаг* Tod448, Kalm *шалме* MN663a (< *čildaġ ← OldT *tiltaġ* C494a.

3.11. Non-regular phonetic correspondences

Due to the limited number of examples, not all phonetic changes that Turkic loanwords have undergone in Mongolic can be classified as regular. In most cases, to recognize Turkic copies in Mongolic and their “return” to Kyrgyz, in addition to phonetic features, one has to resort to etymological, morphological, and semantic criteria, as in the case of the following examples.

Kyrg. *arča* “juniper, cypress” ← M, cf. LM. *arča*, HMog *арц* Lu305b, Bur *арса* Ch65a, Ojr *арца* Tod35, Kalm. *арц* ← OldT *artuč* (?*arduč*) “the juniper tree”, probably through metathesis and back-formation, i.e. *artuč* > *arčut* > *arča*) >> TT. *ardıç* “id.”

Kyrg. *aruu, aruun* “clean, pure, clear; neat, pretty” ← M, cf. MM (MA) *ari’un* P105, LM *ariġun* “cleanliness, purity, chastity; clean, pure, clear; chaste; sinless, holy, sacred” L53b, HMog. *ариун* LU295a, Bur *арюун* Ch68a, Ojr *эрүүн* Tod49, Kalm *арүн* Mn70b ← OldT *arī-* “to be, or become, clean, pure” C198a. According to Rybatzki (2011:192) the morphology of the word (in Mongolian) shows that it is a Turkic loanword of the second (between IX-XII centuries) or third layer (after XIII century).

Kyrg. *boġoo* “fetters, shackles” ← M, cf. MM (IM) *baġū* “bracelet” P433a, LM. *baġui, baġu, buġui* “forearm, wrist; bracelet”, HMog. *буғуй, буғуу* “дистальный конец предплечья, предплечье; запястье; (>) буғуйвч “браслет; наручники, кандалы; ошейник ожерелье” Lu427ab, Bur. *бугааг* “браслет” Ch119a, Kalm. *buġū* Ram58a ← OldT *buqaġu* “fetter, leg-iron, handcuff” (< *buqa-ġu*) C314a, cf. EMT *buqaġu* “fetter(s)” Boesch 95b-96a.

Kyrg. *čeen, ičen* “hibernaculum, hole, burrow; hibernation” ← M, cf. *ičege(n)* “hollow (in a tree), den, haunt, lair (such as may be used by animals for hibernation); hibernation” L397a HMog *ичээ(н)* Lu442a, Bur *эшээ(н)* Ch742b, Ojr *ичөөн* Tod177, Kalm *ичөн* Mn275b (< M. *iče-*, cf. LM “to retire into hibernation; to become torpid (of

animals, birds, etc.)” L397a ← OldT *iče- (<ič “the interior, or inside (of something)” + A-).

Kyrg. *čekit* “dot, point” ← M, cf. LM *čeg*, *čig* a dot, point, period; a Mongolian punctuation mark corresponding to a comma” L168b, HMog. *цэг* Lu1545b, Bur. *сэг* 415b, Kalm. *цег* Mn630b, ← OldT *čāk* “Punkt, Interpunktionszeichen (auch Äquivalent von Skt. *bindu* ‚Tropfen‘) || *nokta*, *noktalam* *işareti* (Skt. *bindu*, “damla”nın da eş değeri)” W226a ← Tib. *tsheg* (W226a, L168b). Kyrg. form < *ček* + (*it* “M plural”.

Kyrg. *joro*, *joro* “omen, augury; sign” ← M, cf. MM (MA) *ira* (*ira=irq* “дурное знамение”) P242b, LM *iru-a*, *iruu-a*, *irv-a* “foreboding, bad omen, premonition” L415a, HMog. *ёр* Lu267b, Bur. *ёро* Ch244b, Ojr. *ўор* Tod185, Kalm. *ўор* Mn280a ← OldT. *iru*, *irü* “Merkmal, Zeichen, Anzeichen, Omen, Orakel, Lakşana, Schönheitszeichen || *işaret*, *belirti*, *alamet*, *kehanet*, *Lakşana*, *güzellik işareti*“ W291, 310)

4. Back borrowings of Early Middle Turkic origin

There are no precise phonetic criteria to distinguish Turkic borrowings of Old Turkic and Early Middle Turkic periods from each other in Mongolic. That is why, for example, Rybatzki (2011: 185-202) is hesitant in most cases when talking about the second and third layers of Turkic borrowings in Mongolic. He relies upon whether the word in question is a Buddhist religious or a chancery term or a new cultural notion. Likewise, Kara (2001: 73-120) takes into account these criteria when distinguishing Late Medieval Turkic elements in Mongolic.

Taking these criteria into consideration the back borrowings in Kyrgyz below can be classified as belonging to the early middle Turkic layer in Mongolic.

Kyrg. (dial) *ada* “evil spirit; disaster” (*ada bol-* “to be scared, frightened”) Muk77b ← M, cf. LM *ada* “evil spirit; demon, devil; object of aversion; nuisance, obstacle, hindrance” L9, HMog. *ađ* Lu177b, Bur. *ađa* Ch31a, Ojr. *ада* (I-II) Tod21, Kalm. *ađ* Mn27b ← OldT. *ada* “Schaden, Not, Gefahr, Bedrohung, Bedrängnis, Beschwarnis, Hindernis, Widrigkeit, Widriges || *zarar*, *sıkıntı*, *güçlük*, *tehlike*, *zor durum*, *üzüntü*, *engel*, *zorluk*, *terslik*, *aksilik*, *ters bir şey*” W6a.

Kyrg. *darbiz*, *darbis* “watermelon” ← M, cf. MM (HY) *arbus* “pastèque” Lew10, LM *tarbus* “watermelon” L780, HMog. *mapеac* LU918a, Bur. *apбyз* (< Rus. *apбyз*) Ch62a, Ojr. *mapеac* Tod314, Kalm. *mapеc* Mn478a ← OldT **arbus*, **qarbus*, EMT *qarpuz* Boesch240b ← Pers. *ħarbūz*. Kyrg., Kaz. (dial.) *darbiz*, Uzb. *tarvuz* and Uyg. *ta(r)vuz* ← WestM where *q-* > *t/d-* is typical (see SIGTJa 2001: 138), while Kaz. *qarbiz* is Turkic.

Kyrg. *erden* (dial.) “an ingot of silver, gem” ← M, cf. MM (HY) *ārdini* “pierre précieuse, objet précieux” Lew15, LM *erdeni* “treasure, jewel, gem; precious” L320b, HMog. *эрдэнэ* Lu1713b, Bur. *эрдэни* Ch735b, Ojr. *эрдени* Tod478, Kalm. *эрднь* Mn702b ← OldT *ārdini* (← Skt. *ratna*) “Juwel, Edelstein, Kleinod, Kostbarkeit || *mücevher*, *değerli taş*, *değerli şey*; aus *Juwelen* || *mücevherden*” W112b. According to Rybatzki (2011: 193) *ārdini* should be categorised as a (Turkic) loanword of the third layer as it belongs to the religious terminology.

Kyrg. *keşik* “fortune; fate, destiny; share, quota” ← M, cf. MM (SH) *keşikten* (< *keşik*) “Leibwächter, Leibgarden”, LM *kesig* “grace, favor, blessing; good luck or good fortune; turn (one’s place, time, or opportunity in a scheduled or alternating order)” L460a, HMog. *xuuuz* L1311a, Bur. *хэуэе* Ch632b, Kalm. *кууз* Mn303b ← EMT. *käzig* “turn; taking turns” Boesch167b >> Kyrg. *kezüü* “herding on a rotational basis”.

5. Conclusion

First, it should be noted that the examples mentioned here do not include all Mongolian back borrowings in Kyrgyz. As mentioned earlier we have focused on identifying phonetic criteria that facilitate the identification of back borrowings based on similar phonetic changes to which certain words had been subjected.

Thus, the great number of Mongolian copies of ultimately Turkic origin in Kyrgyz indicates the following:

1. Lexical copies from Turkic to Mongolic developed asymmetrically in favor of Turkic in the pre-Old Turkic and Old Turkic periods.

2. With the expansion of the Mongolian states during the 13-15 centuries, the Mongol-speaking penetrated the Turkic speaking tribes, especially those that would later form the Kazakh and Kyrgyz nations.

3. Until the 18th century, there was probably Turco-Mongol bilingualism, especially in the Tien-Shan and adjunct areas. This becomes evident not only in the number of loanwords, but also in the way some Turkic words in Kyrgyz not found in Mongolian sources also have phonetic shapes according to Mongolian phonotactics.

ABBREVIATIONS

Alt.	Altai
B	Baskakov
BasInk	Baskakov & Inkizhekova-Grekul
L.	Lessing
Bask.	Baskakov
Boesch.	Boeschoten
Bur.	Buriat
C.	Clauson
Ch.	Cheremisov
DeC	Pavet de Courteille
EMT	Early Middle Turkic
H	Haenisch
HY	Houa-yi yi-yu
HMog.	Khalkha Mongolian
J	Januzakov
IM	Ibn Muhanna
Kalm.	Kalmuck
Kaz.	Kazakh
Khak.	Khakass
Kyrg.	Kyrgyz
Lew	Lew
LM	Literary Mongolian
Lu.	Luvsandendev
M	Mongolic
MA	Muqaddimat al-Adab
MM	Middle Mongolian
Mn.	Muniev
Muk.	Mukambayev
Ojr.	Ojrat
OldT	Old Turkic
P	Poppe 1938
Pek	Pekarskiy

PT	Proto-Turkic
Ram.	Ramstedt
SH	Secret History
T	Turkic
Ten.	Tenishev
Tod.	Todajeva
Trkm.	Turkmen
TT	Turkey Turkish
Tuv.	Tuva
←	copied from
→	copied as
<	developed from
>	developed into
>>	the same etymon also survives as

BIBLIOGRAPHY

BASKAKOV Nikolaj, KARRIJEV Baymuhammet (1968), *Turkmensko-russkij slovar'*, Sovjetskaja Ensiklopedija, Moskva.

BASKAKOV Nikolaj & INKIZHEKOVA-GREKUL Anastasija (1953), *Xakassko-russkij slovar'*, Gosudarstvennoje Izdatel'stvo Inostrannyx i Natsional'nyx Slovarej, Moskva.

BOESCHOTEN Hendrik (2022), *A Dictionary of Early Middle Turkic*, Brill, Leiden-Boston.

CHEREMISOV Konstantin (1951), *Burjat-mongol'sko-Russkij slovar'*, Gosudarstvennoje Izdatel'stvo Inostrannyx i Natsional'nyx Slovarej, Moskva.

CLARK Larry (1980), Turkic loanwords in Mongol. I: The treatment of non-initial s, z, š, č, *Central Asiatic Journal*, Volume XXIV, No. 1-2, pp. 36-59.

CLAUSON Gerard (1959), The Earliest Turkish Loan Words in Mongolian, *Central Asiatic Journal*, Volume 4, No. 3, pp. 174-187

CLAUSON Gerard (1960), The Turkish Elements in 14th Century Mongolian, *Central Asiatic Journal*, volume 5, no. 4, pp. 301-316.

CLAUSON Gerard (1962), *Turkish and Mongolian studies*, Royal Asiatic Society of Great Britain and Ireland, London.

CLAUSON Gerard (1972), *An Etymological Dictionary of Pre-Thirteenth-Century Turkish*, Clarendon Press, Oxford.

CLAUSON, Gerard (1957), The Turkish Y and related sounds, in: *Studia Altaica. Festschrift für Nikolaus Poppe zum 60. Geburtstag am 8. August 1957. (Ural-Altäische Bibliothek 5)*, Harrassowitz Verlag, Wiesbaden, pp. 33–45.

COURTEILLE Pavet de (1870), *Dictionnaire turk-oriental: destiné principalement à faciliter la lecture des ouvrages de Bâber, d'Aboul-Gâzi et de Mir-Ali-Chir-Nevâi*, Imprimerie Impériale, Paris.

CSÁKÍ Éva (2006), *Middle Mongolian Loan Words in Volga Kipchak Languages*, Harrassowitz Verlag, Wiesbaden.

DOERFER Gerhard (1963-1975), *Türkische und mongolische Elemente im Neupersischen*, Volume I-IV, Franz Steiner, Wiesbaden.

ERDAL Marcel (2004), *A Grammar of Old Turkic*, Brill, Leiden-Boston.

GERZENBERG, Leonard (1974), Ob issledovanii rodstva altajskix jazykov, *Voprosy jazykoznanija*, No. 2, pp. 46-55.

HAENISCH Erich (1939), *Wörterbuch zu Mangḡol un Niuca Tobca'an (Yüan-Ch'ao Pi-Shi) Geheime Geschichte der Mongolen*, Otto Harrassowitz, Leipzig.

JANUZAKOV Telgoja (1999), *Kazak tiliniñ sözdigi*, Dajk-Press, Almaty.

KALUZIŃSKI Stanislaw (1961), *mongolische Elemente in der jakutischen Sprache*, Państwowe wydawnictwo naukowe, Warszawa.

KARA György (2001), Late Medieval Turkic Elements in Mongolian, in: Bazin L. & Zieme P. (ed.) *Silk Road Studies V. De Dunhuang a Istanbul. Hommage à James Russell Hamilton*, Brepols, Turnhout, pp. 73-120.

KHABTAGAEVA Bajarma (2009), *Mongolic Elements in Tuvan*, Harrassowitz Verlag, Wiesbaden.

KINCSES NAGY Eva (1996), Mongolian Loanwords in Chagatay, in: Berta A. & Horvath E.(ed.), *Historical and linguistic interaction between Inner-Asia and Europe: proceedings of the 39th Permanent International Conference (PIAC), Szeged, Hungary, June 16-21, 1996*, Department of Altaic Studies, University of Szeged, Szeged, pp. 139-145.

KINCSES NAGY Eva (2018), *Mongolic Copies in Chaghatay*, Harrassowitz Verlag, Wiesbaden.

LEWICKI Marian (1959), *La langue Mongole des Transcriptions Chinoises du XIV^e siècle le Houa-yi yi-yu de 1389*, Państwowe wydawnictwo naukowe, Wrocław.

LUVSANDENDEV Amgaagijn (2001-2002) (ed.), *Bol'šoj Akademičeskij Mongol'sko-Russkij Slovar' v četyrex tomax*, Academia, Moskva.

MUKAMBAYEV Jeembaj (2009), *Kyrgyz tilinin dialektologijalyk sözdügü*, Girne American University Turkish Research and Publicity Centre, Bishkek.

MUNIEV Bembe (1977), *Kalmytsko-Russkij slovar'*, Izdatel'stvo Russkij jazyk, Moskva.

NEMETH, Gyula (1912a), Die türkische-mongolische Hypothese, *Zeitschrift der Deutschen Morgenländischen Gesellschaft*, Volume 66, No. 4, pp. 549-576.

NEMETH, Gyula (1912a), Egy mongol-török hangtörvényhoz, *Nyelvtudományi Közlemények* XLI. kötet, 4. füzet, pp. 401-412.

NEMETH, Gyula (1914), Török-mongol nyelviszonyhoz, *Nyelvtudományi Közlemények* XLIII. kötet, 1. Füzet, pp. 126-142.

PEKARSKIY Eduard (1958), *Slovar' jakutskogo jazyka* Tom I, Vypuski 1-4, Akademija Nauk SSSR, Moskva.

POPPE Nicholas (1938), *Mongol'skij slovar' Mukaddimat al'-Adab, čast' I-II*, Izdatel'stvo Akademii Nauk SSSR, Moskva-Leningrad.

POPPE Nicholas (1955), The Turkic loan words in Middle Mongolian, *Central Asiatic Journal*, Volume 1, No. 1, pp. 36-42.

POPPE Nicholas (1969), On Some Vowel Correspondences in Mongolian Loan-Words in Turkic, *Central Asiatic Journal*, Volume 13, No.3, pp. 207-214.

RAMSTEDT G. John (1935), *Kalmükisches Wörterbuch*, Suomalais-Ugrilainen Seura, Helsinki.

RASSADIN Valentin (1980), *Mongolo-burjatskije zaimstvovanija v sibirskix tjurkskix jazykax*, Nauka, Moskva.

RASSADIN Valentin (2007), *Očerki po istorii složenija tjurko-mongol'skoj jazykovej obščnosti. 1. Tjurkskoje vlijanije na leksiku mongol'skix jazykov*, Elista, Kalmytskij gosudarstvennyj universitet.

RASSADIN Valentin (2008), *Očerki po istorii složenija tjurko-mongol'skoj jazykovej obščnosti. 2. Mongol'skoje vlijanije na leksiku tjurkskix jazykov*, Elista, Kalmytskij gosudarstvennyj universitet.

RASSADIN Valentin (2014), *Altaistika* (Učebnoje posobije), Kalmytskij gosudarstvennyj universitet, Elista.

RÓNA-TAS András (1974), Obščee nasledie ili zaimstvovanija? (K probleme rodstva altajskix jazykov), *Voprosy jazykoznanija*, No. 2, pp. 31-45.

RYBATZKI Volker (2011), Classification of Old Turkic loanwords in Mongolic, in: Ölmez et al (ed.) *Ötüken'den İstanbul'a Türkçenin 1290 Yılı (720-2010). 3-5 Aralık 2010, İstanbul, Bildiriler. From Ötüken to Istanbul. 1290 Years of Turkish (720-2010). 3-5 December 2010, Istanbul, Papers*, Istanbul Büyük Şehir Belediyesi, Istanbul, pp. 185-202.

SCHÖNIG Claus (2000), *mongolische Lehnwörter im Westoghusischen*, Harrassowitz Verlag, Wiesbaden.

SCHÖNIG Claus (2003), Turko-Mongolic relations, in: Janhunen J. (ed.) *The Mongolic Languages*, Routledge, London-New York, pp.403–419.

SCHÖNIG Claus (2005), Türkisch-mongolische Sprachbeziehungen. Versuch einer Zwischenbilanz. *Ural-Altäische Jahrbücher*. N. F., pp. 131–166

SYROMJATNİKOV Nikolaj (1975), Kak otlichit' zaimstvovanija ot iskonnyh obščnostej v altajskix jazykah, *Voprosy jazykoznanija*, No.3, pp. 50-61.

SHCHERBAK Aleksandr (1996), Irregular sound correspondences in Turkic languages conditioned by reborrowing from Mongolian, in: Berta A. et all (ed.) *Symbolae Turcologicae Studies in Honour of Lars Johanson on his Sixtieth Birthday*, Swedish Research Institute, Uppsala, pp. 199-203.

SHCHERBAK Aleksandr (1997), Rannije tjurko-mongol'skije jazykovyje svjazi (V-XIV vv.), Nauka, Sankt-Petersburg.

SHCHERBAK Aleksandr (1999), Turkology and Altaistics, in: Fujishiro S. & Shogaito M. (ed.) *Issues in Turkic Languages. Description and Language Contact*, Department of Linguistics Kyoto University, Kyoto, pp. 9-18.

SHCHERBAK Aleksandr (2005), *Tjurksko-mongol'skije jazykovyje kontakty v istorii mongol'skix jazykov*, Nauka, Sankt-Petersburg.

TATARINTSEV Boris (1976), *Mongol'skoje jazykovoje vlijanije na tuvinskuju leksiku*, Tuvinskoye knizhnoye izdatel'stvo, Kyzyl.

TEKIN Talat (1960), Omuz kelimesi hakkında, *Türk Dili*, No. 104, pp 402-403.

TENIŠEV Edhjam (1968), *Tuvinsko-russkij slovar'*, Izdatel'stvo Sovjetskaja Ensiklopedija, Moskva.

TODAYEVA Buljaš (2001), *Slovar' jazyka oiratov Sin'tszjana*, Kalmytskoje Knizhnoje Izdatel'stvo, Elista.

ÖLMEZ Mehmet (2019), Eski Uygurca *körşî*'nin günümüz Türk ve Moğol dillerindeki karşılığı *körşi* "komşu", in: Oganova E. A. (ed.) *Sözüm Munda Qalir, Barir Bu Özüm... Scripta in Memoriam D.M. Nasilov*, Izdatel'stvo MBA, Moskva, pp. 268-276.

ÜNAL Orçun (2016), *Klasik Moğolca Söz Varlığında Türkçe Kökenli Kelimeler ve Türkçe-Moğolca Ses Denklikleri*, Marmara Üniversitesi Türkiyat Araştırmaları Enstitüsü Türk Dili ve Edebiyatı Anabilim Dalı Türk Dili Bilim Dalı Yayınlanmamış Doktora Tezi.

VLADIMIRTSOV Boris (1912), Turetskije elementy v mongol'skom jazyke, *Zapiski Vostočnago Otdelenija Imperatorskago Russkago Arxeologičeskago Obščestva*, Volume 20 (1910), pp. 153-184.

WILKENS Jens (2021), *Handwörterbuch des Altuigurischen Altuigurisch – Deutsch – Türkisch. Eski Uygurcanın El Sözlüğü Eski Uygurca – Almanca – Türkçe*, Universitätsverlag Göttingen, Göttingen.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

**Funded by
the European Union**

The paper was written as part of the research project titled “Turkic - Mongolian Language Contact: The Case of Kyrgyz”, which received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 101024434.